

A Study to Assess Patients' Satisfaction with the Preoperative Anaesthetic Evaluation

Susheela Taxak¹, Elizabeth James², Abhishek Kalra³, Divya Rajput⁴, Shikha⁵, Nancy Rathi⁶

¹Senior Professor, Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, PGIMS, Rohtak

^{2,3}Senior Resident, Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, PGIMS, Rohtak

^{4,5,6}Junior Resident, Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, PGIMS, Rohtak

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Abhishek Kalra

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Aims: Evaluation of patients' satisfaction is an important aspect for monitoring quality improvement in anaesthesia services which is affected by the preoperative anaesthetist visit significantly. This study aimed to determine the level of patients' satisfaction with the preoperative anaesthetist visit.

Materials and Methods: The present cross-sectional, observational study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, after obtaining approval from Institutional Ethical Committee. Patients of either sex aged between age group 20-70 years (40.62±13.48 years) who underwent elective surgeries in various surgical specialties were included. Data were collected using a questionnaire for patients' satisfaction with the preoperative anaesthetist visit. Collected data were analysed using SPSS software.

Result: In the present study, proportions of males and females were 52.8% and 47.3% respectively among total 400 patients. Regarding satisfaction level of patients with preoperative anaesthetist visit, we found that 92.4% males and 90.5% females were satisfied, 92.6% urban patients were satisfied while 90.3% rural patients were satisfied. 93.0% patients were satisfied in the age range of 20-30 years followed by 91.4% in the range of 30-40, 62.2% in the range of 40-50, 91.2% in the range of 50-60, and 90.5% in the range of 60-70. Patients who had previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia were more satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$). 87.8% patients were satisfied with time given by anaesthetist, 90.8% patients were satisfied with anaesthetist answers to questions, 91% patients felt comfortable after anaesthetist visit and 91.5% patients were satisfied with preoperative anaesthetist visit.

Conclusion: It is concluded that most of the patients were satisfied with preoperative anaesthetist visit.

Keywords: Preoperative Anaesthetic Evaluation, Preoperative Anaesthetist Visit, Patient's Satisfaction.

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Introduction

Evaluation of Patient's satisfaction is an important aspect for monitoring quality improvement in anaesthesia services which is affected by the preoperative anaesthetist visit significantly. This visit enables the anaesthetist to gather information about the patient's general status and type of surgery. It also helps to choose the type of anaesthesia, to discuss perioperative complications and their management with the patient. [1]

Preoperative anaesthetic evaluation is an important part of anaesthetic provision. This helps the patients to get familiar with their anaesthesiologist, to know about anaesthesia options, to discuss postoperative pain, nausea, and vomiting management options and other possible complications. This also decreases patient's anxiety, the chances of the cancellation of surgery

by surgeons and anaesthesiologists and may also reduce complication rates and mortality. [2] It also helps to determine potential anaesthetic difficulties and allays fear of the patient. [3] One of the most important roles of the anaesthesiologist is to perform a preoperative evaluation of the patient and "clear" them for anaesthesia. Initially, the focus was to assess risk for morbidity and mortality based on the presence of clinical factors and to ensure that medical conditions were stable prior to elective surgery.

More recently, there has been an effort to identify interventions that result in improved outcomes in patients with specific comorbidities. [4] Using patient satisfaction as an indicator to monitor the quality of clinical care has lot of importance. For patients, it represents an evaluation of the health

care experiences based on their own values and perception. [5] For the anaesthesiologist, patient satisfaction can reflect many aspects of care such as bedside skills, efficient attention to needs, participation in decision making, adequate communication and information.

Evaluating patient satisfaction has been considered as an important parameter in the analysis of administered health care services by the medical community. [6] It is important because it may correct existing health care problems; and it can also meet patient's desires and expectations, resolve their speculations, and consequently, increase their trust in existing health care system.

Earlier the role of the anaesthesiologist was perceived to be restricted to the immediate preoperative and intraoperative periods, [7] whereas anaesthesiologists are now considered to have greater involvement in preoperative preparation and postoperative care which would allow earlier detection and treatment of postoperative complications. [8-9]

The evaluation of the quality of patient care, depends upon the level at which the assessment is conducted. [10] The point of view of patient is most important outcome of quality of the services provided to them. The evaluation of patient satisfaction should always be based on the subjective perception of the patient on quality of the process. [11]

Health Concerns are among most important issues in wellbeing of an individual therefore, Poor quality of anaesthesia services may discourage patient from using available services. [12] Patient satisfaction is the balance between expectations and perceptions of what is received. If there was concern, staff must continue to identify, monitor and modify factors that may improve it. Patient satisfaction with anaesthesia services remains the best way to assess the outcome from the patients' point of view. [13] But it is difficult to measure satisfaction especially during the preoperative and intra operative periods.

Patient satisfaction is one of the indicators of the quality of health care provision. Patient's perception about health care systems seems to have been largely ignored by healthcare managers in developing countries.

Patient satisfaction depends upon many factors such as: quality of clinical services provided, behavior of staff, cost of services, hospital infrastructure, physical comfort, emotional support and respect for patient preferences. In our hospital, patients are first assessed in Pre-anaesthesia check-up clinic in the outpatient department and then re-

evaluated the day before surgery in respective wards, with the aim of assessing the patient's medical condition; evaluating the patient's overall health status; determining risk factors related to anaesthesia; educating the patient; discussing the techniques of anaesthesia and available options for postoperative management.

However, to the best of our knowledge, no study has been conducted in our hospital that could show the level of patient satisfaction with the preoperative anaesthetic evaluation. The aim of the present study is to determine the level of patient satisfaction with the preoperative anaesthetic evaluation among patients operated upon under general anesthesia during the study period.

Aim and Objectives

Aim: To assess patients' satisfaction with the preoperative anaesthetic evaluation as per Standards of Royal College of Anaesthetists (ROCA)

Objectives:

Primary Objective: The primary objective was to assess the patient's satisfaction with the preoperative anaesthetic evaluation

Secondary Objective: To correlate the level of satisfaction with the parameters, age group, gender, residence (urban/rural) and previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: The present cross-sectional, observational study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, Pt. B.D. Sharma PGIMS, Rohtak, after obtaining approval from Institutional Ethical Committee. Patients of either sex aged between age group 20-70 years who underwent elective surgeries in various surgical specialties were included.

Patients having cognitive dysfunction or any other inability to finish the questionnaire, very seriously ill patients, patients who required postoperative admission in the intensive care unit and patients who refused to participate in the study were excluded from the study.

Patients Data Collection Method

The patients were interviewed within 6 hrs of surgery & anaesthesia after taking an informed and written consent to participate in the study using a questionnaire based on standards for preoperative anaesthetic evaluation of the patients and were compared with Standards laid down by Royal college of Anaesthetists (ROCA) as mentioned below.

Table 1: RCOA Standards for the preoperative anesthetic evaluation of patients. [14]

Standard Number	Standard	Source	Target
1.	Seen by anaesthesiologist before surgery	RCOA	100%
2.	Self-introduction done by anaesthesiologist	RCOA	100%
3.	Patient history taken by anaesthesiologist	RCOA	100%
4.	Physical examination done by anaesthesiologist	RCOA	100%
5.	Fasting instructions given	RCOA	100%
6.	Awareness of the type of anaesthesia before surgery	RCOA	100%
7.	Awareness about the possible anaesthesia complications	RCOA	100%
8.	Awareness of modes of post-operative analgesia	RCOA	100%
9.	Awareness about the option for PONV (post operative nausea vomiting) management	RCOA	100%

From the patient's response to the questionnaire, we found out whether the following points make any difference in the level of satisfaction of patients with the preoperative anaesthetic evaluation.

- Age group
- Gender
- Residence (Urban/Rural)
- Previous exposure to anaesthesia and surgery

Sample size calculation: Formula used:

$$n = \left(\frac{Z\sigma}{E} \right)^2$$

$$n = \frac{(1.96*0.5)^2}{(0.05)^2}$$

Sample size calculated using the above formula is 384.

Where,

- n = Sample size
- Z = Z-score (using confidence interval of 95%)
- σ = standard deviation
- E = margin of error

Statistical Analysis: The data was coded and entered into Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Analysis was done using SPSS version 20 (IBM SPSS Statistics Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA) Windows software program.

Descriptive statistics including computation of percentages, means and standard deviation was used.

For all statistical tests, a p value less than ≤ 0.05 was taken to indicate a significant difference.

Observations and Results: The following observations were made as under:

Table 2: Age distribution

Age group	Frequency	Percent
20-30	103	25.8
30-40	129	32.3
40-50	58	14.5
50-60	68	17.0
60-70	42	10.5
Total	400	100.0
Mean \pm SD	40.62 \pm 13.48	Range (19-70)

Table 2 shows age distribution of study population.

In the present study, maximum number of patients belonged to younger age group i.e. 129(32.3%) between 30-40 years followed by 103(25.8%) who had age between 20-30 years. A total of 58(14.5%) patients had age between 40-50 years. A total of 68(17%) patients had age between 50-60 years and total of 42(10.5%) patients had age between 60-70 years.

In the present study, male outnumbered female i.e. 211(52.8%) were male and 189(47.3%) female. In the present study 185(46.3%) patients belonged to rural area and 215(53.8%) belonged to urban area. Out of 400 patients, 124(31.0%) have history of

previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia. On inquiring whether the patients were seen by anaesthetist, 362(90.5%) gave their answer as yes while 38(9.5%) were unaware of anaesthetist visit. On inquiring whether anaesthetist introduced him/herself, 224(56.0%) gave their answer in 'Yes'.

A total of 362(90.5%) patients were satisfied when we inquired about their level of satisfaction with the illness history taken by the anaesthetist and 38(9.5%) were not satisfied. Out of 400 patients, 362(90.5%) patients were satisfied after general physical examination done by the Anaesthetist. Only 38(9.5%) patients were not satisfied. All the patients were inquired, whether they received any fasting instructions from the anaesthetist, 281

(70.3%) gave their answer in 'Yes'. out of 400 patient's 257(64.3%) patients were satisfied with type of anaesthesia explained by anaesthetist while 143(35.8%) were not satisfied.

Out of 400 patient's 229(57.3%) patients were satisfied with postoperative complications explained by anaesthetist while 171(42.8%) were not satisfied. A total of 195 (48.8%) patients were given postoperative pain relief information by anaesthetist. Out of 400 patients A total of 172(43.0%) patients were given postoperative

nausea/vomiting information by anaesthetist. On inquiring whether sufficient time was given by anaesthetist, 351(87.8%) patients gave their answer in 'Yes'. Out of 400 patient's 363(90.8%) patients were satisfied with anaesthetist's reply to their questions. Only 37 (9.3%) were not satisfied.

A total of 364(91.0%) patients felt comfortable after anaesthetist visit. Patient's satisfaction with preoperative anaesthetic visit: A total of 366(91.5%) patients were satisfied while 34(8.5%) were not satisfied.

Table 3: Whether Sufficient Time Given by Anaesthetist

		N	Y	Total	Chi square test	P value	
Age (Years)	20-30	N	13	90	103	2.409	0.66
		%	12.6	87.4%	100.0%		
	30-40	N	12	117	129		
		%	9.3%	90.7%	100.0%		
	40-50	N	9	49	58		
		%	15.5%	84.5%	100.0%		
	50-60	N	8	60	68		
		%	11.8%	88.2%	100.0%		
	60-70	N	7	35	42		
		%	16.7%	83.3%	100.0%		
Gender	F	N	24	165	189	0.06	0.79
		%	12.7%	87.3%	100.0%		
	M	N	25	186	211		
		%	11.8%	88.2%	100.0%		
Residency	RURAL	N	26	159	185	1.04	0.307
		%	14.1%	85.9%	100.0%		
	URBAN	N	23	192	215		
		%	10.7%	89.3%	100.0%		
Previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia	N	N	36	240	276	0.52	0.47
		%	13.0%	87.0%	100.0%		
	Y	N	13	111	124		
		%	10.5%	89.5%	100.0%		
TOTAL	N	49	351	400			
	%	12.2%	87.8%	100%			

Table 3 shows satisfaction level of patients with time given by anaesthetist.

Age wise distribution of patients revealed that out of total 103 patients in age group 20-30, 13(12.6%) patients were dissatisfied and 90(87.4%) patients were satisfied. In age range 30- 40 years, out of total 129 patients, 12(9.3%) patients were dissatisfied and 117(90.7%) patients were satisfied. In age range 40-50 years, out of 58 patients, 9(15.5%) patients were dissatisfied and 49(84.5%) were satisfied. In age range 50-60 years, out of total 68 patients, 8(11.8%) patients were dissatisfied and 60(88.2%) patients were satisfied. In age range 60-70 years, out of total 42 patients, 7(16.7%) patients were dissatisfied and 35(83.3%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$). Gender wise distribution of the patients

shows that out of total 211 male patients, 25(11.8%) patients were dissatisfied and 186(88.2%) patients were satisfied. Similarly, out of total 189 female patients, 24(12.7%) patients were dissatisfied and 165(87.3%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Residential status of the study population revealed that out of 185 patients who belonged to rural area, 26(14.1%) patients were dissatisfied and 159(85.9%) patients were satisfied. Out of 215 patients who belonged to urban area, 23(10.7%) patients were dissatisfied and 192(89.3%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$). A total of 124 patients had previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia out of which 13(10.5%) patients were

dissatisfied, and 111(89.5%) patients were satisfied. Similarly, out of 276 patients who had no previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia, 36(13.0%) were dissatisfied and 240(87.0%) were

satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Table 4: Satisfaction Regarding Patient's Questions Replied Properly by Anaesthetist

		N	Y	Total	Chi square test	P value	
Age (Years)	20-30	N	11	92	103	0.99	0.9
		%	10.7%	89.3%	100.0%		
	30-40	N	10	119	129		
		%	7.8%	92.2%	100.0%		
	40-50	N	5	53	58		
		%	8.6%	91.4%	100.0%		
50-60	N	6	62	68			
	%	8.8%	91.2%	100.0%			
60-70	N	5	37	42			
	%	11.9%	88.1%	100.0%			
Gender	F	N	20	169	189	0.75	0.38
		%	10.6%	89.4%	100.0%		
	M	N	17	194	211		
		%	8.1%	91.9%	100.0%		
Residency	Rural	N	19	166	185	0.42	0.51
		%	10.3%	89.7%	100.0%		
	Urban	N	18	197	215		
		%	8.4%	91.6%	100.0%		
Previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia	N	N	27	249	276	0.301	0.58
		%	9.8%	90.2%	100.0%		
	Y	N	10	114	124		
		%	8.1%	91.9%	100.0%		
Total	N	37	363	400			
	%	9.2%	90.8%	100.0%			

Table 4 shows satisfaction level of patients with answers given by anaesthetist to their questions.

Age wise distribution of patients revealed that out of total 103 patients in age group 20-30, 11(10.7%) patients were dissatisfied and 92(89.3%) patients were satisfied. In age range 30-

40 years, out of total 129 patients, 10(7.8%) patients were dissatisfied and 119(92.2%) patients were satisfied. In age range 40-50 years, out of 58 patients, 5(8.6%) patients were dissatisfied and 53(91.4%) were satisfied. In age range 50-60 years, out of total 68 patients, 6(8.8%) patients were dissatisfied and 62(91.2%) patients were satisfied. In age range 60-70 years, out of total 42 patients, 5(11.9%) patients were dissatisfied and 37(88.1%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Gender wise distribution of the patients shows that out of total 211 male patients, 17(8.1%) patients were dissatisfied and 194(91.9%) patients were satisfied. Similarly, out of total 189 female patients,

20(10.6%) patients were dissatisfied and 169(89.4%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Residential status of the study population revealed that out of 185 patients who belonged to rural area, 19(10.3%) patients were dissatisfied and 166(89.7%) patients were satisfied. Out of 215 patients who belonged to urban area, 18(8.4%) patients were dissatisfied and 197(91.6%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

A total of 124 patients had previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia out of which 10(8.1%) patients were dissatisfied, and 114(91.9%) patients were satisfied. Similarly, out of

276 patients who had no previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia, 27(9.8%) were dissatisfied and 249(90.2%) were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Table 5: Patient Felt Comfortable After Anaesthetist Visit

			N	Y	Total	Chi square test	P value
Age (Years)	20-30	N	11	92	103	1.44	0.83
		%	10.7%	89.3%	100.0%		
	30-40	N	9	120	129		
		%	7.0%	93.0%	100.0%		
	40-50	N	5	53	58		
		%	8.6%	91.4%	100.0%		
	50-60	N	6	62	68		
		%	8.8%	91.2%	100.0%		
	60-70	N	5	37	42		
		%	11.9%	88.1%	100.0%		
Gender	F	N	19	170	189	0.48	0.4
		%	10.1%	89.9%	100.0%		
	M	N	17	194	211		
		%	8.1%	91.9%	100.0%		
Residency	Rural	N	20	165	185	1.37	0.24
		%	10.8%	89.2%	100.0%		
	Urban	N	16	199	215		
		%	7.4%	92.6%	100.0%		
Previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia	N	N	25	251	276	0.04	0.95
		%	9.1%	90.9%	100.0%		
	Y	N	11	113	124		
		%	8.9%	91.1%	100.0%		
Total	N	36	364	400			
	%	9.0%	91.0%	100.0%			

Table 5 depicts if patient felt comfortable after anaesthetist visit.

Age wise distribution of patients revealed that out of total 103 patients in age group 20-30, 11(10.7%) patients were dissatisfied and 92(89.3%) patients were satisfied. In age range 30- 40 years, out of total 129 patients, 9(7.0%) patients were dissatisfied and 120(93.0%) patients were satisfied. In age range 40-50 years, out of 58 patients, 5(8.6%) patients were dissatisfied and 53(91.4%) were satisfied. In age range 50-60 years, out of total 68 patients, 6(8.8%) patients were dissatisfied and 62(91.2%) patients were satisfied. In age range 60-70 years, out of total 42 patients, 5(11.9%) patients were dissatisfied and 37(88.1%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Gender wise distribution of the patients shows that out of total 211 male patients, 17(8.1%) patients were dissatisfied and 194(91.9%) patients were satisfied. Similarly, out of total 189 female patients,

19(10.1%) patients were dissatisfied and 170(89.9%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$). Residential status of the study population revealed that out of 185 patients who belonged to rural area, 20(10.8%) patients were dissatisfied and 165(89.2%) patients were satisfied. Out of 215 patients who belonged to urban area, 16(7.4%) patients were dissatisfied and 199(92.6%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

A total of 124 patients had previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia out of which 11(8.9%) patients were dissatisfied, and 113(91.1%) patients were satisfied. Similarly, out of

276 patients who had no previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia, 25(9.1%) were dissatisfied and 251(90.9%) were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Table 6: Satisfaction with Preoperative Anaesthetist Visit

			N	Y	Total	Chi square test	P value
	20-30	N	10	93	103	0.64	0.95
		%	9.7%	90.3%	100.0%		
	30-40	N	9	120	129		
		%	7.0%	93.0%	100.0%		
	40-50	N	5	53	58		
		%	8.6%	91.4%	100.0%		

Age (Years)	50-60	N	6	62	68		
		%	8.8%	91.2%	100.0%		
	60-70	N	4	38	42		
		%	9.5%	90.5%	100.0%		
Gender	F	N	18	171	189	0.48	0.48
		%	9.5%	90.5%	100.0%		
	M	N	16	195	211		
		%	7.6%	92.4%	100.0%		
Residency	Rural	N	18	167	185	0.66	0.41
		%	9.7%	90.3%	100.0%		
	Urban	N	16	199	215		
		%	7.4%	92.6%	100.0%		
Previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia	N	N	24	252	276	0.04	0.83
		%	8.7%	91.3%	100.0%		
	Y	N	10	114	124		
		%	8.1%	91.9%	100.0%		
Total	N	34	366	400			
	%	8.5%	91.5%	100.0%			

Table 6 shows satisfaction level of patients with preoperative anaesthetist visit.

Age wise distribution of patients revealed that out of total 103 patients in age group 20-30, 10(9.7%) patients were dissatisfied and 93(90.3%) patients were satisfied. In age range 30-40 years, out of total 129 patients, 9(7.0%) patients were dissatisfied and 120(93.0%) patients were satisfied. In age range 40-50 years, out of 58 patients, 5(8.6%) patients were dissatisfied and 53(91.4%) were satisfied. In age range 50-60 years, out of total 68 patients, 6(8.8%) patients were dissatisfied and 62(91.2%) patients were satisfied. In age range 60-70 years, out of total 42 patients, 4(9.5%) patients were dissatisfied and 38(90.5%) patients were satisfied.

Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$). Gender wise distribution of the patients shows that out of total 211 male patients, 16(7.6%) patients were dissatisfied and 195(92.4%) patients were satisfied. Similarly, out of total 189 female patients, 18(9.5%) patients were dissatisfied and 171(90.5%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Residential status of the study population revealed that out of 185 patients who belonged to rural area, 18(9.7%) patients were dissatisfied and 167(90.3%) patients were satisfied. Out of 215 patients who belonged to urban area, 16(7.4%) patients were dissatisfied and 199(92.6%) patients were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$). A total of 124 patients had previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia out of which 10(8.1%) patients were dissatisfied, and

114(91.9%) patients were satisfied. Similarly, out of

276 patients who had no previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia, 24(8.7%) were dissatisfied and 252(91.3%) were satisfied. Statistical analysis of all these categories were comparable among each other and found to be not significant ($p>0.05$).

Discussion

Information and dedicated personal care by the anaesthesia team is most crucial factor for patient satisfaction. The Evaluation of any health care system depends on whether one is assessing only the performance of practitioner or opinion of patients is also taken into account. Formulating the appropriate standards and obtaining necessary information are steps to evaluate the "The Quality of Care". [15]

Patient's experiences of health care are very crucial for clinical medicine. If medical treatments succeed only in a limited sense but without benefit to those receiving them, then these interventions are considered to be failed. For this reason, subjective health status measures are used to evaluate impact of the interventions on well-being of patients. Similarly feedback of patients' experiences are required for improvement of quality of health care services.

This study was done to evaluate the interaction between the patient and the anaesthetist. This evaluation allows the anaesthetist to assess the patient's medical condition; evaluate the patient's overall health status; determine risk factors related to anaesthesia; discuss the techniques of anaesthesia and available options for postoperative management and obtain consent. During the preoperative evaluation, the patient can get a clear understanding of the planned anaesthesia and the complications that might arise in the perioperative

period. Problems which will be identified during this evaluation process may also be solved before surgery, or, sometimes, surgery may be delayed. All these processes can improve anaesthesia safety, which contributes greatly to a better outcome for surgical patients.

In this study, males were found to be more satisfied than females. This could be due to the fact that they interact more actively and extract more information as compared to females. This finding is in line with the study conducted by Singh et al [16] in 2007 where they too have found males to be more satisfied than females. But a study done by Gebremedhn et al [17] and Ubaradka et al [18] showed higher levels of satisfaction in females.

In our study, three hundred and fifty one patients (87.8%) were satisfied with time given by anaesthetist. The male patients and younger patients were more satisfied with time given by anaesthetist. Urban patients were more satisfied as compared to rural patients. It was also noted in our study that patients who had previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia were more satisfied with time given by anaesthetist.

In our study, three hundred and sixty three patients (90.8%) were able to ask the questions to the anaesthetist and one hundred and seventy one patients (81.5%) were satisfied with the answers by the anaesthetist. The results observed in our study, however shows a greater percentage of patient being able to ask the questions as well as a higher satisfaction rate with the answers given by the anaesthesiologist than the study conducted by Cooray. [19] The reason of this discrepancy could be due to the shortcomings in their setup where most of the patients were not satisfied with the amount of time spent with the anaesthesiologist. Pre-operative evaluation at our setup focuses on anxiety reduction techniques being used during the preoperative evaluation of the patients.

The information provided by the anaesthetist, the adequacy of time spent by the anaesthetists with the patients; the adequacy of the anaesthetists' responses to patients' questions; and proper examination of patient by the anaesthetist has also influenced the higher level of satisfaction. Preoperative anxiety that occurs due to lack of adequate information about anaesthesia and surgery is one of the most common causes of patient dissatisfaction in patients undergoing operation, which was adequately explained in our setup therefore our levels of satisfaction were found to be higher. The male population of patients were more satisfied as compared to female patients. The rural patients were more satisfied as compared to urban patients. In our study we also observed that younger population more satisfied with the answers of the anaesthetist. In our study, three hundred and sixty

four patients (91%) felt comfortable after visit by anaesthetist. The male patients and younger patients felt more comfortable. Urban patients felt more comfortable as compared to rural patients. It was also noted in our study that patients who had previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia felt more comfortable after anaesthetist visit.

In our study, three hundred and sixty six patients (91.5%) were satisfied with preoperative anaesthetist visit. The male patients and patients belonging to younger age group were more satisfied. Urban patients were more satisfied as compared to rural patients. It was also noted in our study that patients who had previous exposure to surgery and anaesthesia were more satisfied.

Satisfaction for a patient is a fine balance between prior expectations, followed by perceptions of the quality of health care which was actually received. [11] Higher patient satisfaction sets the benchmark for protocols and approaches toward a patient, whereas poor satisfaction indicates the need for improvement of overall patient care standards. [16] Thus, it is an important measure of the quality of health care. Satisfaction with anaesthesia is used as an outcome measure in clinical trials. [20] Patient satisfaction is considered to be an integral part of service quality. Its measurement is also required to fulfil performance improvement and revalidation agendas for health care professionals. [12] Most of the patients in our setup were satisfied with the history taken and physical examination done by the anaesthetist.

In our setup to ensure patient safety a mandatory visit by an anaesthetist is done one day prior to surgery as a part of anxiety reduction technique, re-evaluation of patient for any co-morbid conditions, discussing plan for anaesthesia and providing instructions for fasting to the patients. Two hundred and eighty one patients (70.3%) patients received fasting instruction in our setup. However, the Results of our study is lower than the study conducted by Vyhunthan et al [2] where 94.39% of the patients received fasting instruction. The reasons of this discrepancy emphasis on the drawback in our-setup where sufficient number of patients were not able to receive pre-operative fasting instruction due to communication gap between patient and the anaesthetist.

When choosing a questionnaire to use in clinical practice or for research purposes, there are a number of considerations that must be taken into account. Successful completion of a satisfaction questionnaire with minimal missing data is an indication of the clinical acceptability of the tool, thereby supporting its use in practice. Although the optimal length of time to complete an assessment is not clear, a shorter questionnaire that maintains a good level of validity and reliability with simple

and easy-to-understand vocabulary is likely to be less of an imposition for patients who are asked to complete it. A validated yet brief questionnaire will be more suitable for audit and quality-improvement purposes, whereas more detailed questionnaires, providing more information, may be more valuable as outcome measures in clinical trials. In areas of anaesthesia practice, where there is a range of well-developed tools to choose from, we have made recommendations based on instruments that may be used in the quality-improvement. However, there are many branches of anaesthesiology where further work is required on the development and/or validation of satisfaction measures is required.

Limitation

Our study has the following limitations. There was no randomisation in our study. There would have been a way to take care of the bias of the rater as well as the many biases arising out of patients' and caregivers' preference for a specific anaesthetic technique. We could not systematically study the reasons for patient's dissatisfaction. The types of surgeries done were also heterogeneous and the influence of the same on patient satisfaction was not measured. The decision on postoperative stay was primarily taken by surgical team probably based on the wound healing and we did not explore the other possible factors affecting the length of the hospital stay.

Suggestions

Patients at our-setup report high satisfaction with preoperative and perioperative anaesthetic experiences. Level of perceived care can be further increased by either providing more information to the patient or by improving the communication skills at the physician end. The problem of unawareness among the general population regarding the role of anaesthetist should be given emphasis. Anaesthetists should give all the patients a chance to choose type of anaesthesia and should tell any possible side effect and complication related to anaesthesia. Furthermore, studies should be conducted with large sample size.

Conclusion

A large number of patients were satisfied with the preoperative anaesthetic evaluation in our study. However, a study comprising of more number of patients excluding biases like type of surgery and duration of surgery and anaesthesia technique is preferred for further study.

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